

Effect of curvature on nonlinear magnetization dynamics in submicrometer-sized rings

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MIRJA GRANFORS
geboren am 18.07.1998 in Badelunda, Schweden

Institut für Ionenstrahlphysik und Materialforschung Helmholtz-Zentrum
Dresden - Rossendorf
Fakultät Physik
Bereich Mathematik und Naturwissenschaften
Technische Universität Dresden
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1. Gutachter: Prof. Dr. Jürgen Fassbender
2. Gutachter: Prof. Dr. Manfred Helm

Abstract

One of the interesting characteristics of spin waves, which are collective elementary excitations in magnetic materials, is their nonlinear interaction. Moreover, topological and curvature-induced effects are gaining increasing attention in the emerging field of curvilinear magnonics. The aim of this thesis is to study the interplay between a topological effect, the Berry phase, and nonlinear dynamics such as three magnon scattering in a magnetic ring in the vortex state. Here, a Berry phase appears when a static external field perpendicular to the ring is applied. The influence on three magnon scattering is studied by first obtaining spin-wave eigenmodes for different external out-of-plane fields. Second, important characteristics, such as the damping of the modes, are calculated. With those results splitting coefficients and thresholds of the three-wave splitting are calculated in order to predict scattering channels and to estimate the splitting threshold. It is found that, along with the appearance of a Berry phase, certain selection rules of three-wave splitting in vortices are relaxed; moreover, the threshold microwave fields to excite nonlinear dynamics are drastically decreased.

Zusammenfassung

Eine interessante Eigenschaft von Spinwellen, den kollektiven Elementaranregungen in magnetischen Materialien, ist ihre nichtlineare Wechselwirkung. Darüber hinaus gewinnen topologische und krümmungsinduzierte Effekte in dem aufstrebenden Gebiet der krummlinigen Magnonik zunehmend an Aufmerksamkeit. Das Ziel dieser Bachelorarbeit ist die Untersuchung des Zusammenspiels zwischen topologischen Effekten und nichtlinearer Dynamik, hier am Beispiel der Berry-Phase und der Dreimagnonenstreuung in einem magnetischen Ring im Vortex-Zustand. Hier tritt eine Berry-Phase auf, wenn ein statisches äußeres Feld senkrecht zum Ring angelegt wird. Der Einfluss auf die Dreimagnonenstreuung wird analysiert, indem zunächst Spin-Wellen-Eigenmoden für verschiedene externe Felder senkrecht zum Ring ermittelt werden. Weiterhin werden wichtige Eigenschaften wie die Dämpfung der Moden berechnet. Mit diesen Ergebnissen werden Aufspaltungskoeffizienten und benötigte Mikrowellenfelder der Dreimagnonenstreuung bestimmt, um Streukanäle vorherzusagen und den Grenzwert der Aufspaltung abzuschätzen. Es wird festgestellt, dass mit dem Auftreten einer Berry-Phase bestimmte Auswahlregeln der Dreimagnonenstreuung gelockert werden und zusätzlich die Schwelle des Mikrowellenfeldes zur Anregung der nichtlinearen Dynamik drastisch verringert wird.

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1 Motivation

The study of curvature-induced effects on spin-wave dynamics is a relatively young field. It has been found that surface curvature can lead to various interesting effects, such as stabilizing magnetic skyrmions and asymmetric spin-wave dispersion [1], [2]. On the other hand, magnetization dynamics inherit intrinsic non-linearities such as multi-magnon scattering [3]. Those effects are of interest for example for neuromorphic computing. However, the interplay between geometric and nonlinear effects in spin-wave dynamics is mostly unknown. In this thesis both linear characteristics such as damping of the spin-wave eigenmodes and nonlinear effects influenced by the Berry phase, including three wave scattering, are studied using a combination of micromagnetic simulation and analytical calculations. The three wave scattering, which is the splitting of one spin-wave mode into two other spin-wave modes, can take place if a spin-wave eigenmode is excited above a certain threshold power and certain selection rules are fulfilled. This leads to well defined scattering channels. These selection rules, and thereby also the splitting channels and their thresholds, can be influenced by the Berry phase. To exclude the effect of the vortex core, in other words to study only the effects of the Berry phase, a ring is chosen for the calculations in this thesis.

2 Theoretical background

In this thesis three magnon scattering in a ring-shaped sample is investigated using micromagnetic simulations. Similar studies have already been made before in vortex-state disks, but to highlight the effects of the Berry phase and to exclude the effect of the vortex core a ring is chosen.

This theoretical part of the thesis will begin by introducing the main interactions in micromagnetic samples. Hereafter the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation of motion, which describes the dynamics of the magnetic moments, is introduced and linearized. Furthermore, the Berry phase is described briefly. In the last part of this chapter the multi-magnon scattering and the quantities used to analyze it are presented.

2.1 Magnetism, ferromagnetism and fundamental interactions

Magnetic order in a material at room temperature can not be explained by classical theory but is a result of the quantum mechanical exchange interaction. All materials are either diamagnetic or paramagnetic. The latter has the characteristic that the elementary magnetic moments of the substance can be orientated in the direction of the field by an external magnetic field. There are some paramagnetic materials that spontaneously form ordered structures, even without an external field. Ferromagnetism is the simplest type of those. This spontaneous magnetic order is near ideal only at low temperatures. At higher temperatures the thermal motion prevents the ordered orientation of the magnetic moments [4].

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of the magnetization in the ring with no external field applied. The grey arrows represent the approximate orientation of the magnetization.

In micromagnetism magnetic behavior is examined on the nanometer and micrometer scale, for which most calculations can be performed within a continuum limit. Within this limit a continuous magnetization vector field \mathbf{M} is considered instead of individual magnetic moments. The main interactions of ferromagnets at this scale are the exchange interaction, the dipolar interaction and the interaction with the external field. Together, these interactions can be considered as an effective magnetic field $\mathbf{B}_{\text{eff}} = \mathbf{B}_{\text{exch}} + \mathbf{B}_{\text{dip}} + \mathbf{B}_{\text{ext}}$. The exchange interaction is the main reason for the magnetic order, with the exchange energy being minimal if the spins are aligned parallel [4]. The dipolar interaction favors a reduction of stray fields, which in some samples lead to a splitting of the magnetization into domains. In the micrometer-sized ring with a high aspect ratio, for which magnetic effects are investigated in this thesis, the interplay of exchange and dipolar interactions form a so-called vortex state, for which the magnetization configuration is shown in figure 2.1. In the following course the cylindrical coordinate system, also shown in the figure, is used.

2.2 Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation

To investigate magnetization dynamics, first the Landau-Lifshitz equation is introduced. The magnetization \mathbf{M} changes in time if it is not parallel to the effective field \mathbf{B}_{eff} [5]. The change in time is proportional both to the cross product of \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{B}_{eff} , which describes the precessional character of the magnetization around the effective field, as well as to the gyromagnetic ratio γ and the vacuum permeability μ_0 [5]. This leads to the lossless Landau-Lifshitz equation

$$\frac{d\mathbf{M}}{dt} = \gamma\mu_0 [\mathbf{M} \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{eff}}]. \quad (2.1)$$

This form of the equation is energy conserving, which means that the magnetization would precess forever. Nevertheless, it is clear that this motion could not continue forever if for example damping, due to the transfer of energy from the precessing spin system to lattice vibrations, is involved. The loss of energy can be introduced phenomenologically into this torque equation. A component of $d\mathbf{M}/dt$ in the direction which minimizes the cone angle is needed, since this would imply that the magnetization would be driven towards an equilibrium state with $\mathbf{M} \parallel \mathbf{B}_{\text{eff}}$ [5]. A mathematically particular convenient solution is the one found by Thomas L. Gilbert, which leads to the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert (LLG) equation

$$\frac{d\mathbf{M}}{dt} = -\gamma [\mathbf{M} \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{eff}}] + \frac{\alpha_G}{M_s} \left[\mathbf{M} \times \frac{d\mathbf{M}}{dt} \right], \quad (2.2)$$

in which α_G is the phenomenological, dimensionless and material-dependent Gilbert damping constant and M_s is the saturation magnetization [5].

2.3 Linear spin-wave dynamics

The Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation can be linearized by first splitting the magnetization into a static and a dynamic part $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \mathbf{M}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{r}) + \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and only keeping the terms up to first order in the dynamic component $\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ [6]. The effective field \mathbf{B}_{eff} is split into a static and a dynamic component in the same way ($\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \mathbf{B}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{r}) + \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{r}, t)$). This gives the linearized LLG equation [6]

$$\frac{d\mathbf{m}(t)}{dt} = -\gamma[\mathbf{M}_{\text{eq}} \times \mathbf{b}(t) + \mathbf{m}(t) \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{eq}}]. \quad (2.3)$$

This equation is solved by

$$\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} (\mathbf{s}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} t} + \text{c.c.}), \quad (2.4)$$

where ‘‘c.c.’’ indicates the complex conjugate of the first term [6]. In this solution \mathbf{k} is the wave vector, $\mathbf{s}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the spatial mode profile and $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$ is the angular frequency of the spin-wave mode [6].

Figure 2.2: Examples for determination of radial and azimuthal mode numbers. The z-component of the magnetization is shown, from which the mode numbers (a) $n = 0$, $|m| = 3$ and (b) $n = 1$, $|m| = 5$ can be determined. The colorbars indicate the value of the z-component of the magnetization in Tesla. The mode profiles were obtained using TetraEigen, as explained in section 3.2.

The spin-wave modes can be categorized by radial and azimuthal mode numbers in cylindrical magnetic samples, such as a ring or a disk. The modulus of the azimuthal mode number $|m|$ is the number of azimuthal periods and the radial mode number n is the number of nodal points in the radial direction. Two examples of mode profiles are shown in figure 2.2.

2.4 Damping of spin-wave eigenmodes and ellipticity

The nonlinear interaction between spin-waves modes not only depends on the coupling between the modes but also on their life times. For the study of nonlinear interactions of spin-wave modes the damping of these modes is therefore essential. This magnetic damping can be taken into account rigorously, but it is rather complicated due to the various mechanics of energy dissipation [7]. Usually it is considered phenomenologically instead, which can be done in the following way if the damping is small in comparison to the frequency. Then the damping

$$\Gamma_\nu = \alpha_G \epsilon_\nu \omega_\nu \quad (2.5)$$

is dependent on the Gilbert damping parameter α_G , the mode frequency ω_ν and the ellipticity ϵ_ν [7]. This leads to a decay of mode amplitudes proportional to $e^{-\Gamma t}$ [8]. This approach describes the magnetic damping in bulk ferromagnetic samples relatively well, within the limits of relatively small damping rates and small magnitudes of the dynamic magnetization [7].

The ellipticity ϵ_ν describes the deviation of the magnetization precession from the circular precession. In the case of a spatially uniform magnetization precession the ellipticity coefficient ϵ is directly linked to the eccentricity \mathcal{E} [7]

$$\epsilon = 1 + \frac{\mathcal{E}^2}{2(1 - \mathcal{E})}. \quad (2.6)$$

The precession eccentricity is defined as $\mathcal{E} = 1 - (|m_{\min}|^2/|m_{\max}|^2)$, where m_{\min} and m_{\max} are the small and the large axis of the elliptical precession, respectively [4]. If the precession is circular ($\mathcal{E} = 0$), obviously ϵ is equal to 1. For elliptically polarized magnetization precession ϵ increases and thereby the damping of the spin-wave mode becomes larger than $\alpha_G \omega_\nu$.

Considering the magnetization dynamics of a finite sized ferromagnetic sample one finds that the spin-wave modes of the sample satisfy the condition

$$\langle \mathbf{s}_{\nu'}^* \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu} \times \mathbf{s}_\nu \rangle = -i A_\nu \delta_{\nu, \nu'}, \quad (2.7)$$

where ν is used to enumerate the spin-wave eigenmodes, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the spatial distribution of the normalized equilibrium magnetization, A_ν is the real normalization constant of a spin-wave eigenmode and “ $\langle \dots \rangle$ ” is denoting the volume average [7]. By using the volume average of the magnitude of the profile of an eigenmode and the real normalization constant from equation (2.7) the ellipticity for a spin-wave eigenmode is obtained [7]

$$\epsilon_\nu = \frac{\langle |\mathbf{s}_\nu|^2 \rangle}{A_\nu}. \quad (2.8)$$

2.5 Berry phase

In this thesis the effect of the Berry phase is studied on the nonlinear spin-wave interaction in magnetic rings. The occurrence of the Berry phase in rings was predicted theoretically by Dugaev *et al.* [9]. For vortex state disks with an external out-of-plane (OOP) field it has been shown that modes with opposite azimuthal mode numbers m are split in frequency [10].

The eigenfrequency of a spin-wave mode is depending on the azimuthal profile of the eigenmode in the sample (a ring in thesis), that can be described using the azimuthal mode number m as introduced in chapter 2.3. Two modes with the same absolute value of the azimuthal mode number, assuming that they have the same radial profile, are degenerate in frequency for the vortex ground state if no external field is applied. This degeneracy is lifted by the Berry phase originating from the exchange interaction if a field is applied and the ring thereby evolves into a helical state. The evolution of the equilibrium magnetization in a ring in the presence of an external field in the OOP direction is sketched in figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Schematic representation of the effect of an external field on the magnetization in the ring with **a)** no external field, **b)** an external OOP field smaller than the value of the saturation magnetization and **c)** an external OOP field equal to or larger than the saturation magnetization.

As shown by Zaspel *et al.* [11] and Ivanov *et al.* [10] modes with the azimuthal mode numbers $m = \pm 1$ in a vortex state disk have different frequencies due to the impact of the vortex core. In this thesis a ring was chosen intentionally to avoid the influence of the vortex core on the spin-wave eigenmodes, thereby only frequency splitting between the modes due to the Berry phase occurs.

2.6 Multimagnon scattering

The linearization of the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation is used to obtain eigenfrequencies and mode profiles. However, the initial LLG equation is nonlinear, so spin-wave dynamics are nonlinear, too. A spin wave, also called a magnon, always perturbs the medium that it is propagating in and thereby influences the effective field [6]. That means that the effective field that the spin waves are exposed to changes. The intrinsic non-linearity of the magnetization dynamics in ferromagnetic materials can lead to a variety of different phenomena [12].

With a relatively small external driving field the nonlinear magnetization dynamics can be treated as interactions of several linear spin-wave eigenmodes. Thereby the nonlinear spin-wave dynamics can be studied in the quasi-particle picture where nonlinear processes are described as interactions of linear spin-wave eigenmodes [6]. The multimagnon interactions with the highest impact on the system are often the lowest order three or four magnon interactions [12], for which a schematic diagram is shown in figure 2.4. These scatterings have to fulfill conservation of both energy and momentum. In other words the sum of the frequency ω of the decaying mode(s) (called primary mode(s)) has to be equal to the sum of the frequencies of the modes that are decayed into (called secondary modes)[6]. The wave vector \mathbf{k} has to be preserved in the same manner for the momentum to be conserved

$$\sum_{\text{in}} \omega_i = \sum_{\text{out}} \omega_j \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{\text{in}} \mathbf{k}_i = \sum_{\text{out}} \mathbf{k}_j. \quad (2.9)$$

Figure 2.4: Schematic representation of **a)** a three magnon scattering and **b)** a four magnon scattering [6].

In this thesis three magnon scattering is studied for decays of primary modes for which the azimuthal mode number is zero (also called radial modes). For the angular momentum to be conserved for these scatterings the azimuthal mode numbers m_1 and m_2 of the two secondary modes have to be of opposite sign, $m_2 = -m_1$ [12]. In addition to this selection rule and the conservation of energy has to be conserved, there is a third condition, namely that the radial indices n_1 and n_2 of the secondary modes have to be different: $n_1 \neq n_2$ [13]. This selection rule is valid if there is no external field applied to the sample, but in the case of an added OOP-field it is relaxed, which is discussed in chapter 5.

There is often a threshold in amplitude, due to the intrinsic damping of the spin-wave modes, that needs to be overcome for the multi magnon scattering to take place [6]. This is discussed in section 2.6.2. But first an important quantity, the so-called three-wave splitting coefficient, which is needed for the calculation of the threshold, is introduced.

2.6.1 Three wave splitting coefficients

In spin-wave spectra that are relatively dense it is likely that the resonance condition of conserved energy is satisfied approximately for several different pairs of secondary modes [12].

Here, approximately means that the named condition is fulfilled with the accuracy of the frequency line width of the spin-wave eigenmodes. Verba *et al.* derived an expression for the so-called three-magnon coefficients [12]. This enables the calculation of the power threshold of the splitting and the determination which splitting channels would be observed in experiments [12].

The three-magnon term of the Hamiltonian writes as [3]

$$\mathcal{H}^{(3)} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{123} (U_{123} c_1 c_2 c_3 + \text{c.c.}) + \sum_{123} (V_{12,3} c_1 c_2 c_3^* + \text{c.c.}). \quad (2.10)$$

The first term describes the explosive instability of the spin-wave modes whereas the second term, which is relevant for this thesis, describes the splitting of the spin-wave mode 3 into the spin-wave modes 1 and 2 [12]. This splitting is written as $3 \rightarrow (1+2)$ in a short notation. ‘‘c.c.’’ denotes the complex conjugate of the preceding term. The coefficient of the three-wave splitting $V_{12,3}$ is dependent on the normalized linear spin-wave eigenmodes \mathbf{s}_ν , the spatial distribution of the normalized static equilibrium magnetization $\boldsymbol{\mu} = \mathbf{M}_0(\mathbf{r}, t)/M_s$ (where \mathbf{M}_0 is the static equilibrium magnetization and M_s is the saturation magnetization) and the tensor $\hat{\mathbf{N}}$ that describes the magnetic self interactions, such as exchange, dipolar and anisotropy interaction, [12]

$$V_{12,3} = \frac{\omega_M}{2V_d} \int \left((\mathbf{s}_2 \cdot \mathbf{s}_3^*) \boldsymbol{\mu} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{N}} \cdot \mathbf{s}_1 + (\mathbf{s}_1 \cdot \mathbf{s}_3^*) \boldsymbol{\mu} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{N}} \cdot \mathbf{s}_2 + (\mathbf{s}_1 \cdot \mathbf{s}_2) \boldsymbol{\mu} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{N}} \cdot \mathbf{s}_3^* \right) d^3r. \quad (2.11)$$

The factor ω_M is the product of the gyromagnetic ratio γ , the vacuum permeability μ_0 and the saturation magnetization M_s and V_d is the volume of the sample [12].

Both the spatial profiles and the frequencies ω_ν of the eigenmodes can be obtained from the solution of the linearized Landau-Lifshitz equation. Before the spatial profiles are used to calculate the coefficient of the three-wave splitting, they have to be normalized to fulfill the relation

$$\frac{i}{V_d} \int \mathbf{s}_\nu^* \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu} \times \mathbf{s}_\nu d\mathbf{r} = 1. \quad (2.12)$$

2.6.2 Threshold

Several splitting channels which fulfill the resonance condition approximately for a directly excited primary spin-wave mode might exist. To predict which one of them will be observed in experiments the threshold field is calculated. In a general case of non-resonant splitting the threshold of a certain splitting process is determined by the three wave coefficient, the damping rates of the modes and the detuning. The latter originates from the resonance condition and

has the following form

$$\delta\omega = \omega_p - (\omega_1 + \omega_2), \quad (2.13)$$

where ω_p is the driving frequency, which excites the primary mode [12].

The expression for the threshold field b_ρ , derived from equations (A3) and (A4) of Verba *et al.* [12], is

$$|b_\rho| = \sqrt{\Gamma_1 \Gamma_2 \left(1 + \frac{\delta\omega^2}{(\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2)^2} \right)} \cdot \left| \frac{2\sqrt{(\omega_p - \omega_3)^2 + \Gamma_3^2}}{\gamma \langle s_{3,\rho} \rangle} \right| \cdot \frac{1}{|V_{12,3}|}, \quad (2.14)$$

where $\langle s_{3,\rho} \rangle$ is the averaged dynamic ρ -component of the spin-wave mode 3, which is the mode that is split.

The three-wave splitting is a threshold process, which means that it begins if the amplitude of the mode that is split reaches this threshold field [12]. The channel with the lowest threshold is the one which will be observed in experiments [12]. Even if another channel has a threshold that is only slightly higher it is less likely for that scattering to take place [12]. The reason for this is that when the splitting begins for the splitting channel with the lowest threshold the nonlinear interaction of the spin-wave modes makes the “effective pumping” smaller for the other modes [12]. As a result of that the driving field amplitude needed to observe other channels is significantly larger than the calculated value from equation 2.14 [12].

3 Methods

In this thesis simulations and other numerical calculations are made. In this chapter code developed by the author as well as already existing programs are introduced.

There are different ways to calculate or obtain the spin-wave modes of a confined magnetic sample. It can be done analytically, but for many complex systems only approximations are achievable [14]. Another way is to use dynamic simulations. This can be done, for example, by the time integration of the LLG equation using a Finite-Element Method while an external magnetic field pulse is used to excite oscillation modes in a given geometry [15]. A third method is the dynamic matrix approach. This is done in the program TetraEigen, developed in-house by Gwendolyn Quasebarth [14]. In this thesis TetraEigen is used to obtain the spatial mode profiles and the frequencies of the spin-wave eigenmodes. From the obtained eigenmodes other quantities, such as the damping of spin-wave modes and the three-wave splitting coefficient for magnon splitting, are calculated.

3.1 TetraStat

For determining the equilibrium magnetization of the ring TetraStat, a conjugate gradient based energy minimizer of the TetraMag micromagnetic code, is used [16]. The equilibrium is calculated for several different OOP fields in the interval 0 T to 2 T. The material parameters, which are the material parameters for permalloy, and sizes of the sample used for the simulations are noted in table 3.1. From these equilibrium states the eigenmodes and their frequencies are obtained using TetraEigen, which is described in section 3.2.

<i>Material parameters</i>	
Exchange stiffness	13 pJ/m
Saturation magnetization M_s	800 kA/m
Gyromagnetic ratio γ	176 GHz/T
Gilbert damping	0.008
<i>Dimensions</i>	
Outer radius, inner radius, thickness	250 nm, 50 nm, 20 nm
Discretisation length of the mesh	5 nm

Table 3.1: Material parameters and dimensions of the ring.

3.2 TetraEigen

TetraEigen uses a dynamic matrix approach. It uses an eigen-solver to find spatial mode profiles and frequencies as solutions of the damping-less and linearized LLG equation. A detailed description can be found in the bachelor thesis of Gwendolyn Quasebarth, who implemented TetraEigen [14]. The approach of TetraEigen makes it possible to find energetically degenerate modes and the method does not require the design of special excitation fields [14].

3.3 MuMax

MuMax3 is a GPU-accelerated micromagnetic simulation program [17]. In this thesis it is only used to validate some of the code the author wrote for the nonlinear spin-wave interaction studies, discussed in the following paragraphs. Using finite-difference discretization, which is a special case of the finite element method [14], it solves the space and time dependent magnetization evolution on an orthorhombic grid [17]. The effective field and the magnetization are calculated for each time step. At each time step or at the the end of the simulation the resulting magnetization and other quantities can be stored [17].

The simulations in MuMax are performed by the author using the method described by Wagner *et al.* [18]. The imaginary part of the z-component of the susceptibility χ''_{zz} is proportional to the averaged out-of-plane component of the magnetization when the microwave field is crossing zero

$$\langle \chi''_{zz} \rangle = -\frac{\langle m_z(t_n) \rangle}{h_0}, \quad (3.1)$$

while the real part χ'_{zz} can be obtained similarly a quarter period later where the microwave field reaches its maximum [18]. Here, $h_0 = |\mathbf{b}_0|/\mu_0$ is the modulus of the microwave amplitude.

3.4 Damping calculations

As mentioned before, the damping $\Gamma_\nu = \alpha_G \epsilon_\nu \omega_\nu$ described in section 2.4 is important in calculations of nonlinear spin-wave interactions. The constant material parameter α_G , also called the Gilbert damping parameter, is set to 0.008 in all calculations throughout this thesis. The eigenfrequencies ω_ν of the spin-wave eigenmodes are calculated with TetraEigen as described in section 3.2. The ellipticity coefficient ϵ_ν is calculated with a script written by the author based on the equations 2.7 and 2.8. To crosscheck these calculations for ϵ_ν , the susceptibility is calculated as well. The imaginary part of the susceptibility is then compared to the same quantity calculated by MuMax. For this comparison two rectangular cuboid samples are investigated. One smaller, for which simulations are done rather quick, and one larger, for which the simulations contain more information. The sizes of the samples are listed in table 3.2, where also the simulation parameters are given. The material parameters are the same as for the ring, see section 3.1.

	Small rectangle	Large rectangle
Size	200 nm x 50 nm x 10 nm	1 μ m x 200 nm x 30 nm
Frequency	8.8 - 31.6 GHz	2 - 30 GHz
<i>MuMax simulation</i>		
Number of cells	64 x 16 x 1	128 x 32 x 1
Frequency steps	0.01 GHz	0.01 GHz
<i>TetraStat simulation</i>		
Discretisation length	5 nm	5 nm
Frequency steps	0.005 GHz	0.005 GHz

Table 3.2: Sizes and simulation parameters of the rectangles.

For both simulations the susceptibility is determined in the presence of an external field, once when the external field is parallel to the long axis of the rectangle (the so-called easy axis) and once for an external field parallel to the short axis (the hard axis). The applied field is 200 mT in all cases, except for the simulation of the large rectangle with the external field applied along the hard axis, where the field is set to 300 mT, to ensure saturation along this axis. The equilibrium magnetization for each rectangle in each applied field is determined using TetraStat, and the eigenmodes are obtained using TetraEigen.

The z-component (OOP component) of the susceptibility of each mode is calculated with the following equation

$$\chi_{\nu,zz} = \frac{1}{A_\nu V_d} \sum_{i,j} m_{\nu,z,j}^* m_{\nu,z,k}, \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.1: Comparing calculations made with TetraEigen with results from MuMax. The comparison is done for four different scenarios: for a smaller rectangle cuboid, where the external field $B_{\text{ext},z} = 200$ mT is **a)** applied parallel to the long axis and **b)** applied along the shorter axis, and for a larger rectangle cuboid, where **c)** the external field $B_{\text{ext},z} = 200$ mT is applied along the long axis and **d)** the external field $B_{\text{ext},z} = 300$ mT is applied parallel to the shorter axis.

where $m_{\nu,z,i}$ are the z -components of the spatial profiles of the spin-wave eigenmodes. The total susceptibility of the sample is given by

$$\chi_{zz}(\omega) = \gamma\mu_0 M_s \sum_{\nu} \frac{\chi_{\nu,zz}}{(\omega_{\nu} - \omega) - i\Gamma_{\nu}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where ω is the driving frequency [19]. The damping Γ_{ν} is calculated from ϵ_{ν} as written before, which makes it suitable for testing the calculation of the ellipticity coefficient ϵ_{ν} . This susceptibility is compared to the same quantity obtained with MuMax using a numerical FMR method [18] as shown in figure 3.1, where there is one diagram for each executed combination

of rectangle size and direction of the external field.

From figure 3.1 it is clear that both methods have very similar results, especially for the larger rectangle. One of the reasons why there is a slight difference in the resulting eigenfrequencies is that the methods use different meshes and numerical methods to compute the interaction fields. By replacing a few of the eigenfrequencies with those obtained by MuMax in the calculation of χ_{zz} , a perfect agreement for the line width is obtained (figure 3.2). The quantitative agreement confirms that the damping calculation from the eigenmodes implemented by the author is correct.

Figure 3.2: Comparing calculations made with TetraEigen with the results from MuMax for the larger rectangle cuboid with the external field $B_{\text{ext},z} = 300 \text{ mT}$ applied along the shorter axis. For the calculations from the TetraEigen modes six of the eigenfrequencies were replaced by the frequencies of the peaks of the MuMax simulation.

3.5 Calculations of the three wave splitting coefficient

To calculate the thresholds of the splitting channels for the spin-wave modes first the three-wave splitting coefficient has to be calculated. The resulting splitting coefficients are later used by the author to calculate the threshold according to equation (2.14).

A script is written by the author for the calculation of the splitting coefficient based on equation (2.11). It is using the equilibrium magnetization obtained from TetraStat and normalizing the mode profiles obtained by TetraEigen. For the calculations the tensor \hat{N} , which describes the magnetic self interactions, is taken from the TetraEigen code-base.

4 Linear characteristics

This chapter will start with examining the equilibrium magnetization states in the ring as a function of an applied static external field followed by the calculation of the corresponding spin-wave eigenmodes. Hereafter the categorization of the eigenmodes is described and how their eigenfrequencies change if an external field is applied. Lastly, the ellipticity coefficient, which is needed for the calculations related to nonlinear characteristics of the modes in the following chapter, is computed.

4.1 Equilibrium magnetization

The examination of the linear characteristics begins by investigating the overall magnetization equilibrium states as a function of an applied field in the OOP direction, which is the z-direction (perpendicular to the plane of the ring) in this thesis. The average in-plane and out-of-plane components of the magnetization extracted from the simulations are plotted as a function of the applied field $B_{\text{ext},z}$ in figure 4.1. One can see that the saturation magnetization is reached if the z-component M_z of the magnetization is becoming 1, while the φ -component M_φ becomes zero, at around 925 mT.

Figure 4.1: The φ - and z-components of the magnetization in the ring, plotted against the applied external field $B_{\text{ext},z}$.

4.2 Mode spectrum

To enable calculations linked to the nonlinear dynamics of the modes some of the mode characteristics have to be examined.

For each spin-wave eigenmode obtained from TetraEigen the azimuthal mode number m and the radial mode number n are determined. The main approach to this is to observe the components of the magnetization as shown in figure 2.2. For several external OOP fields a few spatial eigenmode profiles and their eigenfrequencies are computed using TetraEigen. For some field values, namely for $B_{\text{ext},z} = 0, 100, 200, 400, 800, 1000$ and 1500 mT, a large number of modes and their associated frequencies are obtained.

From the number of azimuthal periods alone it is not possible to determine the sign of the azimuthal mode number m , but only its absolute value. To enable the separation of the modes with different signs of the same $|m|$ a script was written by the author to perform a polar Fourier transform (PFT) of each mode profile. The PFT has a peak at the azimuthal mode number of the mode. Two examples for this can be displayed in figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Results from the PFT, with an external OOP field is $B_{\text{ext},z} = 800$ mT, for two modes with $|m| = 3$. From these plots their azimuthal mode numbers can be determined, in this case (a) $m = -3$ (b) $m = 3$.

Applying this method to all eigenmodes that are investigated in this thesis gives some unexpected results. With no external field applied the PFT has more than one peak. In figure 4.3 there are examples of the PFT with no outer field for two different modes with the same absolute value of the azimuthal mode number m . From this it is not possible to determine which of the modes has the positive sign and which has the negative sign of the azimuthal number, because each of them has two peaks for opposite signs of the mode number, at the positions -3 and $+3$ in the example. The reason for this is purely mathematical: when TetraEigen determines the mode profiles from the LLG-equation it calculates a set of eigenvectors, but

the eigensolver does not know a priori how the modes are categorized. In the case of no external field, this means that those eigenvectors are degenerate and can be chosen from a two-dimensional eigenspace. Therefore each eigenvector is a superposition of $+m$ and $-m$. When the degeneracy is lifted with the addition of an external field, which will be discussed in section 4.3, this effect is not present anymore.

Figure 4.3: Results from the PFT, with the external OOP field $B_{\text{ext},z} = 0$ mT, for two modes with $|m| = 3$. From these plots only the absolute value of their azimuthal mode numbers can be determined to be **(a)** $|m| = 3$ and **(b)** $|m| = 3$.

A different problem occurs if a large external field is applied. Two examples are plotted in figure 4.4 for an OOP-field of 1 T, which is slightly larger than the saturation magnetization. The plotted examples of the PFT are also for the modes where the absolute value of the azimuthal mode number is 3, as in the examples above. The highest peaks are at the positions for these azimuthal numbers, but there are a lot of other peaks in addition to that. The cause for that could be that the in plane component of the magnetization becomes smaller with a larger external OOP-field, as pictured in figure 4.1.

It is still possible to determine which of two modes with the same radial index and same absolute value of the azimuthal index m is the mode with the negative m and the mode with the positive m in the case of a large external field. For this purpose the sign of m is first determined for all modes when a field is applied for which it is clear from the PFT, for example with $B_{\text{ext},z} = 800$ mT. This gives the result that all modes with a negative m have a higher frequency than those with a positive m for the ring examined in this thesis, which is caused by the difference in exchange energy of the modes when a field is applied. The difference in exchange energy is induced by the Berry phase, and it enables the determination of the sign of the azimuthal index for modes where a large external field is applied.

Figure 4.4: Results from the PFT, with an external OOP field of $B_{\text{ext},z} = 1$ T, for two modes with $|m| = 3$. From both plot (a) and (b) the azimuthal mode numbers can not be determined, even though an azimuthal mode number $m = -3$ can be guessed in (b).

4.3 Dispersion of the modes

In the following, the evolution of the spin-wave eigenfrequencies under an external OOP-field is examined. This is first done by determining the frequency of a few modes for several different fields. This shows both lifting of the degeneracy in energy and crossing of energy levels. After that, the frequencies in dependence of the mode numbers are investigated for some selected fields, which shows even clearer that the degeneracy in energy is lifted.

For several field values of the OOP-field $B_{\text{ext},z}$ the mode profiles are categorized for 15 modes with the lowest frequencies. The evolution of the modes frequency with the radial index $n = 0$ and absolute value of the azimuthal indices from 0 to 3 are shown in figure 4.5. This plot shows that the mode frequencies decrease in general for all modes if an external field, smaller than the saturation magnetization, is applied. There is a small exception for the modes with a negative azimuthal index m if a small field is applied. For an increasing field larger than the saturation magnetization the frequency of all modes increase linearly instead.

In figure 4.5, it is observable that the degeneracy in energy of modes with opposite m is lifted with the addition of an external OOP-field. With no field applied the modes with the same radial index and the same absolute value of the azimuthal index m have the same frequency, while they have different frequencies in the presence of the OOP-field. The reason for the lifting of the degeneracy is the Berry phase.

It is only a technical issue that the mode with the azimuthal mode number 0 does not appear until the field has reached a certain value. This is because only the first 15 modes with the lowest frequencies were categorized (not all of them are shown in figure 4.5), as mentioned before, and for lower external fields this mode is not within the modes with the lowest frequen-

Figure 4.5: Eigenfrequencies, sorted by the mode profile indices, in dependence of the external field $B_{\text{ext},z}$. All the plotted modes have the radial index $n = 0$.

cies. The mode which has the lowest frequency of all the existing eigenmodes for an applied field is varying for different fields. This is already known from similar studies with vortex-state disks [20]. The effect known as level crossing between spin-wave modes is clearly visible for the mode with the azimuthal mode number 0 in this plot, but takes place for some of the other modes as well.

For certain external fields more mode profiles are categorized and their frequencies are plotted depending on their azimuthal indices m and radial indices n in figure 4.6. This extended study of the eigenmodes up to the 7th radial index as a function of the external field is used in the following chapter to study the nonlinear interaction of spin-wave modes. The same effects can be observed as in figure 4.5, even though the character of the plot is different. The frequency of a mode first decreases as the field is increased, but only until the saturation magnetization is reached. From that point on the frequencies increase. It is noticed that in the case of no or only a small external field the modes with the absolute value of the azimuthal mode numbers 3 or 4 are lowest in energy. This changes as the external field is increasing. For larger fields modes with lower absolute value of the azimuthal mode numbers have the lowest energy. This again indicates the level crossing of the spin-wave modes. The lifting of the degeneracy due to the Berry phase is also clearly visible in figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: The eigenfrequency of the eigenmodes plotted over the modulus of the azimuthal mode index m . The data points are colored to associate them with their radial mode index n . The scale of the y-axis is differing for the last plot, where $B_{\text{ext},z} = 1.5$ mT. The lines are a guide to the eye, where some are dotted to distinguish between a positive and a negative m .

4.4 Ellipticity

For the calculations of the threshold field the damping, and thereby also the ellipticity coefficient, is needed. The ellipticity is calculated by the author, as described in section 3.4. The results with no external field applied are shown in figure 4.7. In this figure the same quantity is plotted for a vortex-state disk, with a diameter of 5.1 μm , a thickness of 50 nm and the same material parameters as the ring, for comparison. The ellipticity coefficients of the eigenmodes of the disk were calculated analytically by Roman Verba [7].

Figure 4.7: The ellipticity coefficient ϵ in dependence of the azimuthal mode number is plotted for the eigenmodes in **a)** the ring and **b)** a vortex-state disk. The ellipticity of the modes in the vortex-state disk were obtained by Roman Verba. No external field is applied.

The ellipticity coefficients for the ring and the disk, as pictured in figure 4.7, are of course differing due to the different shapes and sizes of the samples, but also have similarities. Even though the modes of the two samples have different ellipticity coefficients, all of them are in the single-digit range (and are of course larger or equal to one, which they have to be by definition). Two other similarities are that the coefficient is largest for modes with the radial mode number 0 and becomes smaller as the number increases and that the maximum is reached when the azimuthal mode number is relatively low, but not zero.

5 Nonlinear effects

In this chapter the thresholds of the splitting channels are calculated, which is synonymous with calculating which splitting channels will be realized if an experiment is done. To achieve this, first the possible scattering channels are predicted. Second, the three-wave splitting coefficients, the detuning and the smallest line width for the different channels are calculated. The last step is the determination of the thresholds. The coefficients as well as the threshold fields are evaluated in dependence of the static OOP field.

5.1 Possible scattering channels

To predict if there are any splitting channels for which the selection rules are fulfilled (see section 2.6) a script originally written by Lukas Körber [6] is used. This checks if the resonance condition $\omega_3 = \omega_1 + \omega_2$, the conservation of angular momentum $m_1 = -m_2$ for $m_3 = 0$ and the selection rule $n_1 \neq n_2$ are satisfied for a pair of secondary modes 1 and 2, by testing if all conditions are fulfilled for different excitation frequencies f_{RF} . The results with no external field and with an external OOP field of 400 mT are displayed in figure 5.1. Here also the modes with $m = 0$, which are the modes for which the decay is investigated, are plotted.

Figure 5.1: Possible scattering channels when **a)** no external field is applied **b)** the external field is 400 mT, based on the selection rules $\omega_3 = \omega_1 + \omega_2$, $m_1 = -m_2$ and $n_1 \neq n_2$. The modes with $n = 0$, which are the modes for which the decay is investigated, are plotted in addition to that.

One finds that the conditions are fulfilled for many pairs of secondary modes at a given RF frequency. Some of the primary modes, the ones with a low radial number n ($n < 5$), have a frequency which is too low to be able to fulfill the resonance condition. Therefore there are no possible splitting channels for those in contrast to channels with a primary mode with a higher radial index ($n \geq 5$).

For the two different field values the possible splitting channels look similar. The frequencies, both for the decaying modes as well as for the secondary modes, are differing slightly, which can be explained by the fact that the frequency is decreasing in general for an applied field smaller than the saturation magnetization, as discussed in section 4.3. It has to be noted that the selection rule $n_1 \neq n_2$ is relaxed if an external field is added, which will be discussed in paragraph 5.4. This is not considered in these calculations, which means that the plotted scattering channels are only an approximation for which channels are fulfilling the selection rules in the case of an added external field.

5.2 Calculation of the three-wave coefficients

The next step to enable the calculation of the threshold is to explicitly calculate the three-wave splitting coefficients. For this purpose, all eigenmodes included in the calculations have to be categorized by their azimuthal and radial mode numbers.

As discussed earlier, in section 4.2, there is a problem of determining the sign of the azimuthal mode number of a mode if no external field is applied. In that case the modes with the same radial and azimuthal mode numbers are degenerate and also have spatial profiles that are not connected to one azimuthal mode number, but to two azimuthal mode numbers with opposite signs. To use the mode profiles from TetraEigen one would therefore have to transform those, so that they all have definite azimuthal mode numbers m . Because of this problem, analytical modes, approximated by Bessel functions J_i , are generated, which can be used for the same calculations as the modes generated by TetraEigen. They are:

$$s_\rho = J_1(k\rho)e^{i\varphi m}, \quad s_\varphi = -iJ_1(k\rho)e^{i\varphi m}\cos(\theta) \quad \text{and} \quad s_z = J_1(k\rho)e^{i\varphi m}\sin(\theta),$$

where k is the n th zero of $J_1(x)$ ($x \in (0, \infty)$) divided by the difference of the outer and inner radius of the ring. The angle θ is the average angle of the equilibrium magnetization obtained with TetraStat and m and n are the radial and azimuthal mode numbers. These analytical modes are used for the calculations here. There are some characteristics of the TetraEigen modes that are not seen for the analytical modes. The ellipticity coefficient is always one for the analytical modes and the mode profile looks different in the radial direction. Both of

those characteristics are due to the fact that the analytical modes are constructed by simple mathematical equations, which give approximated profiles.

Figure 5.2: The three-wave splitting coefficient $V_{12,3}$ in dependence of the azimuthal mode number is plotted for three different splitting branches in **a)** the ring and **b)** a vortex state disk. The $V_{12,3}$ for the vortex state disk were obtained analytically by Roman Verba [12]. No external field is applied.

The three magnon splitting coefficients are calculated as described in section 3.5 for the same external fields as before. The results for the decaying of the primary mode with the radial mode number 6 into modes with radial mode numbers $n = 0, 1, 2$ and opposite azimuthal mode numbers when no external field is applied can be seen in the figures 5.3. For comparison the same quantity is plotted for the decay of the primary mode with the radial index 2 for a disk with the diameter $5.1 \mu\text{m}$ and the same material parameters as the ring. The data of the disk have been calculated analytically by Roman Verba [12]. The size and the topology are different for the two samples, which probably is the reason for the differing values of the splitting coefficient $V_{12,3}$. But it can easily be seen that the plots are qualitatively very similar and that that the channels with the lowest $V_{12,3}$ within the branches with $n_1 = 0, n_2 = 1$ and $n_1 = 1, n_2 = 2$ are even the same. Another observation from the plots is that the splitting coefficient changes with both the radial index n and the azimuthal index m , for which the dependency is non-monotonic.

In figure 5.3 it is clear that the splitting coefficient is not only dependent on the radial and azimuthal indices, but also on the external field. For the plotted applied fields $V_{12,3}$ in general becomes larger with a larger external OOP field. This transition is especially interesting for the “forbidden” channels with $n_1 = n_2 = 0$, for which the selection rule $n_1 \neq n_2$ is not fulfilled if no external field is applied. It evolves from having a smaller $V_{12,3}$ than most other channels, if no field is applied, to be among the channels with the highest $V_{12,3}$ when the external field is increased.

Three splitting channels, with fixed azimuthal and radial indices, $(6, 0) \rightarrow (0, 5) + (0, -5)$,

Figure 5.3: three-wave splitting coefficient for the decay of the primary excited radial mode with the radial number 6 into some of the branches with radial mode numbers $n = 0, 1, 2$ for the applied external fields $B_{\text{ext},z} = 0, 100, 200$ and 400 mT.

Figure 5.4: three-wave splitting coefficient for three splitting channels with different applied external OOP-fields..

$(6, 0) \rightarrow (0, 14) + (1, -14)$ and $(6, 0) \rightarrow (1, 8) + (2, -8)$, are shown in figure 5.4 for all used external fields. In this plot it is clearly visible that $V_{12,3}$ changes with the applied field. It is also seen that the coefficient is not only increasing with the application of larger fields, but that it becomes smaller again for fields in the regime where the magnetization in the sample is saturated.

5.3 Detuning and line width

Another important quantity needed to determine the threshold is the detuning $|\delta\omega| = |\omega_p - (\omega_1 + \omega_2)|$. For the sake of simplicity the driving frequency ω_p is set to be equal to the mode frequency ω_3 of the primary excited mode in the calculations in this thesis. By comparing it to the smallest line width, $\Gamma_\nu = \alpha_G \epsilon_\nu \omega_\nu$, of the three modes it is possible to see which scattering channels are resonant and thereby possible to observe in an experiment. The resonate channels are those where the $|\delta\omega|$ is smaller than the smallest line width. As mentioned before the analytical mode profiles do not have any corresponding eigenfrequencies and their ellipticity is always one. Therefore only the mode frequencies and ellipticities obtained using TetraEigen are used in these calculations.

Figure 5.5: Detuning, compared to the smallest line width, for four different primary excited radial modes with the radial indices 0, 3, 5 and 6 with an added external OOP field of 400 mT. The detuning is within resonance if it is smaller than the smallest linewidth.

In figure 5.5 the detuning of the same channels are plotted for 4 different primary modes with an external OOP field of 400 mT. The decaying modes all have an azimuthal mode index $m_3 = 0$ and have the radial indices 0, 3, 5 and 6. As already anticipated in section 5.1 it is seen that the resonance condition is only fulfilled for the decay of radial modes with a high radial index. One can tell from the plot for $B_{\text{ext},z} = 400$ mT in figure 5.1 that the mode with the radial index 0 has no possible scattering channels in that approximation. The same holds for the decaying mode with a radial index of 3, even though it is closer to having possible scattering channels. Although the possible scattering channels plotted in that figure only are approximations if an external field is added, it still corresponds well to the the results of the detuning. It can easily be told for the radial modes with the index 0 and 3 in figure 5.5 that there are no resonant channels. In contrast to that there are resonant channels for the radial modes with the indices 5 and 6, as predicted before. Not all of them are shown in the figure, because only some of the splitting branches are plotted.

Figure 5.6: Detuning, compared to the smallest line width, for the primary excited radial mode with the radial number 6 with an added external OOP field of 0, 100, 200 and 400 mT. The detuning is within resonance if it is smaller than the smallest linewidth.

In figure 5.6, where channels for the decay of the primary excited mode with a radial index of $n = 6$ is plotted for the applied external fields 0, 100, 200 and 400 mT, one finds that the detuning is not only changing with the mode numbers for the primary and secondary modes, but also with the change of the external field. This is likely due to the fact that the mode frequencies become smaller towards saturation.

5.4 Transition of the threshold fields

The threshold is calculated to determine which scattering channels are most likely to be observed in an experiment. Here, the analytical mode profiles and the damping and detuning from the TetraEigen modes are used. The results for some branches for the radial mode with the radial index 6 with the different applied fields $B_{\text{ext},z} = 0, 100, 200$ and 400 mT are plotted in figure 5.7.

Figure 5.7: The calculated threshold for the decay of the primary excited radial mode with the radial mode index 6 into branches where the radial mode numbers are $n = 0, 1, 2$ with an external field of $B_{\text{ext},z} = 0, 100, 200$ and 400 mT are applied. The lowest threshold denotes the most probable scattering channel.

It is shown in the plot that, the most likely scattering channel for the radial mode with a radial mode number $n = 6$, excited at resonance, is $(6, 0) \rightarrow (0, 6) + (2, -6)$ of the plotted channels for no applied external field. This changes to the channel $(6, 0) \rightarrow (0, 13) + (0, -13)$ when an external OOP field is applied. To determine which scattering channel is most likely to be observed for a certain radial mode, one would have to compare the threshold of all possible channels. An important observation that can be made by comparing the thresholds for the different applied fields is that the threshold decreases in general if an external field is applied, especially for the “forbidden” channel where the radial indices of the secondary modes are equal, $n_1 = n_2 = 0$. This indicates that the selection rule $n_1 \neq n_2$ is lifted in the presence of an external OOP field.

It is also of great importance that the threshold for the channel with the lowest threshold is lower for an applied OOP field compared to when no field is applied. This channel is the most interesting one as it is hard to observe any other channels in an experiment, as discussed in section 2.6.2. This means that the needed microwave field to excite these nonlinear dynamics decreases with an applied field. In fact, the decrease of the threshold microwave fields is quite drastic. At a static OOP field of 0 mT, the channels $(6, 0) \rightarrow (0, m) + (0, -m)$ are „forbidden“ in the sense that their threshold field is so large that they are experimentally inaccessible. Applying a microwave field of several thousands of mT would produce serious Joule heating and therefore drastically change the magnetic properties of the sample, up to the point where the material could become paramagnetic. However, at a static OOP field of 400 mT, these threshold fields are reduced to the order of 1 mT or even lower. This means that the application of a static OOP fields makes much more scattering channels experimentally accessible.

Figure 5.8: Threshold for three splitting channels with different applied external OOP-fields.

To investigate the field dependency of the threshold further, the same three channels are chosen as in section 5.2. For these the threshold is plotted for all investigated fields in figure 5.8. Similar to figure 5.7 it is observable that the threshold decreases for those channels in the presence of an external field. But an additional observation is made, namely that the threshold is the smallest at $B_{\text{ext},z} = 800$ mT, where it is approximately 10^{-15} times smaller than for 0 mT. However such low threshold fields are likely unphysical and could be a result of the approximated mode profiles. For field values above the saturation field the threshold field increases but its value is still small.

6 Summary

In this thesis the influence of the Berry phase on spin-wave eigenmodes and on the splitting of one of these primary modes into two secondary modes were investigated. This was done by first creating a sample in form of a ring and by obtaining all eigenmodes and their frequencies with different external out-of-plane (OOP) fields applied. The ring was chosen instead of a vortex state disk, for which three-wave splitting has already been studied, to avoid a lifting of the degeneracy of the mode frequencies due to the influence of the vortex core but only due to the Berry phase. The obtained eigenmodes were categorized and their intrinsic damping was calculated. Owing to the ambiguity in the determination of the azimuthal mode number for quite a few modes analytical mode profiles were created. By using mode profiles, eigenfrequencies, equilibrium magnetization and damping of the modes, the splitting coefficients, the detuning and the thresholds of the splitting processes were calculated.

Figure 6.1 summarizes the main results of this thesis. In the first plot it is clearly visible that the equilibrium magnetization state changes in the sample with the applied external OOP field. It is observed that the sample is saturated, meaning that the magnetization only has an OOP component (the z-component in this case), with an applied field of approximately $B_{\text{ext},z} = 925 \text{ mT}$ and above. In the second plot the influence of the Berry phase is visible. It lifts the degeneracy of modes with opposite signs of the azimuthal mode number m , in the presence of an external OOP field, which are degenerate if no external field is applied. This plot also points out that the frequency decreases in general if a larger external OOP field is applied until $B_{\text{ext},z} = 925 \text{ mT}$ is reached, which is the saturation field. For fields larger than that the frequency as a function of the applied external OOP field has a steep incline.

Both the three-wave splitting coefficient $V_{12,3}$ and the threshold b_ρ are varying with different applied external fields, which is not unexpected as, inter alia, mode frequencies and the damping of those change. The change in both of the plotted quantities in figure 6.1 is most interesting for the channel with equal radial mode numbers $n_1 = n_2 = 0$, as scattering should not take place for this channel according to analytical predicted selection rules if no external field is applied. In the absence of an applied field this is observed as the corresponding three-wave splitting coefficient $V_{12,3}$ is significantly smaller and the threshold b_ρ is larger than for the other channels. With applied external OOP fields this changes, and in chapter 5 it

Figure 6.1: The **a)** average z - and φ -components of the magnetization of the ring, **b)** the frequency for the modes with the radial mode number $n = 0$ and the azimuthal mode numbers $m = -1$ and $m = 1$, **c)** the splitting coefficient $V_{12,3}$ for three splitting channels and **d)** the threshold b_ρ for the same three splitting channels in dependence of the applied external OOP field $B_{\text{ext},z}$.

is shown that the lowest threshold for the studied branches with applied fields is reached for splitting into a channel with equal radial mode numbers. The observation that the threshold decreases in general in the presence of an external OOP field could make it significantly easier to study three wave scattering in experiments, as a smaller microwave field is needed to excite nonlinear dynamics. The threshold appears to decrease until the field where the saturation magnetization is reached ($B_{\text{ext},z} = 925$ mT) and then increases again.

In this thesis it is shown that the influence of the Berry phase lifts the degeneracy of the eigenfrequencies of modes, relaxes the selection rule $n_1 \neq n_2$ for the three-wave splitting and thereby also lowers the threshold field needed to excite the three-wave splitting. To summarize, it can be said that topological effects, such as the Berry phase of spin waves, can have drastic impact on nonlinear magnetization dynamics.

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Selbständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich diese Arbeit im Rahmen der Betreuung am Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden - Rossendorf ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter verfasst und alle Quellen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Mirja Granfors
Dresden, Februar 2021